

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D8.5

Feasibility of X-Rotor Concept

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@XROTORProject

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

List of acronyms

DoA	Description of Action
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OREC	Ocean Renewable Energy Coalition
WESC	Wind Energy Science Conference
WP	Work Package
XRC	X-ROTOR concept

1 Introduction/Description of the Deliverable

This report for Deliverable 8.5 will include input from Strathclyde and GE on the feasibility of the X-Rotor concept based on the project findings. It will combine content from D1.6 “Final Project” and D8.4 “Technology Roadmap Developed” to report on the feasibility of the X-Rotor concept and the feasibility of the next steps in the development process. This deliverable will be considered successfully complete when the report is delivered to the executive management group.

The report consists of a section briefly summarising the project outcomes (further details in D1.6), a section summarising the next steps for the concept development (further details in D8.4) followed by a section authored by both University of Strathclyde and GE on the feasibility of the concept and the feasibility of the proposed next steps in the development of the concept. Lastly the report will include a sign off section for both the University of Strathclyde and GE.

2 Summary of Project Outputs

The XROTOR project was made possible by collaborative efforts across partner institutions on 9 work packages. Through rigorous research, experimentation, and analysis, the project progressed the development and validation of the X-Rotor concept taking the concept from TRL 1 to TRL 3 during the 3 year 4-month project period.

One of the project's major achievements lies in the successful WP2 aerodynamic analysis of the X-Rotor concept. That work, bolstered by CFD predictions and wind tunnel tests, has and will provide valuable insights into the performance and loading characteristics of the X-Rotor. The validation of wake control strategies and the demonstration of potential efficiency gains through Regenerative Wind Farming attest to the concept's promise in enhancing wind farm productivity and viability for high density wind farms.

Furthermore, the design and analysis conducted in Work Packages 3, 4 and 5 have created new tools and yielded crucial insights into the X-Rotor's operation strategy, controller, mechanical structure, power take-off, and conversion system. While initial structural designs met industry standards, opportunities for optimization have been identified, paving the way for potential cost reductions and performance enhancements. Similarly, the detailed analysis and design of power take-off systems have ensured the compatibility, efficiency, and reliability of the X-Rotor's energy conversion mechanisms.

The economic analyses conducted in Work Package 6 have underscored the cost-effectiveness and competitiveness of the X-Rotor compared to traditional horizontal axis wind turbines. Projections of maintenance cost savings and reductions in the levelized cost of energy (LCoE) highlight the X-Rotor's potential to impact the wind energy landscape, offering both economic and environmental benefits. Moreover, the comprehensive assessment of social, economic, and environmental impacts

conducted in Work Package 7 has provided invaluable insights into stakeholder perceptions, economic implications, and environmental considerations associated with the X-Rotor's deployment.

Further details of the project outcomes can be seen in deliverable D1.6.

3 Summary of next steps for X-Rotor Development

The creation of the roadmap for further development of the X-Rotor concept has been a very useful step in defining the next steps for the concept. Full details of the road map development can be seen in Deliverable 8.4. D8.4 represents a collaborative industry wide effort aimed at determining a strategic course for the continued development and eventual commercialization of the X-Rotor technology.

Through the establishment of the X-Rotor Panel of Experts and Industrial Advisory Board (IAB), comprising stakeholders from various sectors including investors, developers, OEMs, operators, consultancies, and research bodies, a diverse array of perspectives provided input to the development of the roadmap for the XROTOR next steps. That collective expertise has been key to identifying the unique selling points (USPs) and challenges facing the X-Rotor concept.

From the insights garnered through engagements with the IAB, actionable recommendations have been formulated to address existing challenges and capitalize on inherent strengths of the concept. These recommendations span both technical and commercial domains.

Looking ahead, the immediate next steps for advancing the X-Rotor concept into Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 4 to 6 involve further design and development work on the two bladed concept and feasibility work on the three-bladed X-Rotor concept, along with the design of a scaled prototype. This prototype, engineered at a 10/1 scale and strategically designed to fit into a standard shipping container, will enable testing in low wind speed sites in Asia. Funding for this phase will be sourced from research grants and ex-oil and industrial partners.

Beyond TRL 6, the development trajectory of the X-Rotor concept is less certain but it is likely it will involve collaboration with existing wind energy companies and/or new entrants as well as exploration of funding avenues such as Horizon Europe, Innovate UK, Royal Academy of Engineering etc. These opportunities will facilitate the realization of full-scale prototypes and provide the necessary resources and support for commercialization.

Whilst many of the models required for the development of the X-Rotor concept were created in this work, further work on both the two bladed and three bladed concepts are key to determining the commercial feasibility of the XROTOR concept. The success of the X-Rotor concept hinges on systematic addressing of technical barriers, strategic collaborations, and emphasis on the concepts unique and diverse advantages.

Further details of the roadmap for further development of the X-Rotor can be seen in deliverable D8.4

4 Discussion and Conclusion on Feasibility of XROTOR and Next Steps

The culmination of the XROTOR project offers an optimistic outlook on the feasibility and potential of the X-Rotor concept in technical terms with further work required to provide certainty on optimal design configuration. Whilst the XROTOR project also points at commercial feasibility an even greater amount of further work is required to determine commercial feasibility of the concept. What can be stated with certainty is that through the extensive research carried out in the XROTOR project, the X-Rotor concept has made notable advancements in design tools and TRL progress, reaching Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 3 within the project period from a starting point of TRL1.

It is the opinion of the XROTOR team from the University of Strathclyde and GE, that the technical findings outlined in D1.6 and summarised in Section 2 of this report point towards the technical feasibility of the concept. Additionally, the next steps of the X-Rotor outlined in D8.4 and summarised in Section 3 of this report are ambitious but also feasible and will move the concept towards commercialisation.

As in all research projects great challenges remain, including the need for further refinement, optimisation and validation of design models and candidate designs, however the results from this XROTOR project instils confidence in the feasibility and potential of the X-Rotor concept.

5 University of Strathclyde and GE Sign Off

Date	Signed off by University of Strathclyde and GE
2024.04.30	William Leithead, James Carroll and Jordi Jové Bellot